

2014

ISSN 2278-5655

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly)

Peer-Reviewed Journal

Impact factor:0.948

Chief-Editor

Ubale Amol Baban

PEER-REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

**[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldham Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near
TV Towar,Badlapur, MSief**

**TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG SECONDARY
SCHOOL TEACHERS: A CO- RELATIONAL STUDY**

Education

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Abstract

The present investigation has been carried out to study the teachers' effectiveness and job satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers. For this purpose a sample of 1000 teachers was randomly selected from the Secondary Schools of Punjab. Teacher Effectiveness Scale by Kumar & Mutha (1999) and Ojha's study of values (1996) scale were used. Job satisfaction of the teachers was evaluated by using Sharma and Singh's Job Satisfaction Scale was used. The findings of the study reveal that highly effective and less effective teachers differ significantly on the basis of their job satisfaction. Highly effective teachers are significantly more satisfied with their job as compared to less effective teachers. Job satisfaction has a positive correlation with positive correlation with teachers' effectiveness. It is suggested that in order to raise the effectiveness of teachers their job satisfaction must be enhanced.

Teacher shapes the destiny of nation by acting as a promoter of change, manager of learning activities and donor of knowledge. The National Policy of Education (1986, 1992) further stipulates, "The status of the teacher reflects the socio-cultural ethos of the society. It is said that no people can rise above the level of the teachers. The government and the community should endeavor to create conditions which will help, motivate and inspire teachers on

constructive and creative lines." In the present era of globalisation, the quality education is prerequisite for the fulfilment of the needs of the society. There are many factors which affect the quality of education like; teacher, curriculum, educational policies, infrastructure of the institutions, finance, methods of teaching, resource management and administrative set up etc. Teacher is the most important factor for imparting the quality education. Only a qualified teacher, who has intimate knowledge of the subject, strong self-discipline, enriched with pedagogical and instructional skills can impart the quality education.

Effectiveness is the combination of various dimensions. It is considered to be an apex of perfection to be desired and looked for in all kinds of activities in which one is engaged. Thus, effectiveness is characterised by optimum level of efficiency and productivity on the part of person concerned. It is an attribute in the person's personality in his best form (Arora 1975). Effectiveness is the yardstick of an individual's creative thoughts, purposeful actions, influential impact and successive pursuits.

Teacher effectiveness refers specifically to the professional characteristics of a teacher. An effective teacher is one, who cannot only impart the entire educational curricula allotted to him in the best and the most efficient manner, but also ensures the best possible academic performance and an optimum development of all round personality of the students. The effectiveness of the educational process depends upon the effectiveness of the teachers. It is the capacity of the teacher to realize some of the educational objectives like; desired pupil behaviour, abilities, habits and characteristics to bring development of basic skills, desirable attitudes and adequate personal adjustment of pupils (American Educational Research Association, 1952).

Flander and Simon (1969) defined teacher effectiveness as an area of research which is concerned with relationship between characteristics of teacher, teaching activities and their efforts in the educational outcomes of classroom teaching. It is a collection of work produced by a teacher to highlight and demonstrate his/her knowledge, skills and contents."

Teacher effectiveness is the ability to make effective use of sound personality patterns and professional insight in relating to children and in promoting their all-round development. It is a very important dimension to improve the quality of teaching. According to encyclopaedia of educational research, teacher effectiveness includes many activities concerned with the teaching and learning processes which are performed by a teacher in an efficient manner. Teacher effectiveness is a matter of degree to which a teacher achieves desired effects upon the students (Michael, 1997)

As pointed by Kumar and Mutha (1973) an effective teacher is a unique human being who is conscious of his role and responsibility as a teacher. Effective teacher keeps good qualities such as buoyancy, considerateness, cooperativeness, dependability, emotional stability, expressiveness and flexibility. He must be in possession of forcefulness, judgement, mental alertness, objectivity, personal magnetism, physical energy, drive and adventuresome spirit.

Job satisfaction is the favourableness or unfavourableness with which employees view their work. It results when there is discrepancy between job requirements and wants and expectations of the employee. It expresses the extent of match between employee's expectations of the job and rewards that the job provides.

Job satisfaction is an attitude which results from a balanced summation of many positive and negative experiences in connection with the job. The concept of job satisfaction has attracted the attention of psychologists as well as industrialists, in view of its high positive relation with the job efficiency and personal happiness of workers. Unless a man is satisfied with the job, it is very difficult for him to carry on his duties effectively. The various specific job factors are (i) intrinsic aspects of job (ii) supervision (iii) working conditions (iv) salary (v) promotions (vi) security (vii) management (viii) Social aspects of job (ix) communication (x) benefits etc.

The most common way of determining an employee's satisfaction with a job is to ask that person if he is satisfied with the work to which he is engaged. From this point of view, "Job satisfaction is any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that causes a person truthfully to say, "I am satisfied with my job." Job satisfaction refers to an

overall effective orientation on the part of individuals towards their work roles, which they are presently occupying. This conceptualisation implies that job satisfaction is a unitary concept, and that individuals may characterised by some sort of vaguely defined attitude towards their total job satisfaction. Job satisfaction being a unitary concept does not imply that causes of this overall attitude are not multidimensional. Obviously, a person may be satisfied with one dimension of the job and dissatisfied with another. The assumption underlying the present view is that it is possible for individuals to balance these specific satisfaction against the specific dissatisfactions, and thus to arrive at a composite satisfaction with the job as a whole (Hoppock, 1935).

The usefulness and effectiveness of the education system largely depends upon the active, resourceful and competent teachers. Teacher's competence, capability and effectiveness make schools good or bad, flourishing or deteriorating. So, quality of teaching depends upon the efficiency of the teachers.

Many researchers intended to find the relationship of teacher effectiveness with job satisfaction Sexena and Jayotsna (1995), Witcher, Ann, Anthony and Lynn (2001) conducted studies on effective and ineffective teachers and found the impact of job satisfaction on their effectiveness. Kukreti, Sexena and Gihar (2005) investigated the job motivation factors of efficient and inefficient teachers and concluded that job motivation is entirely related with the satisfaction from the job whereas motivation led to teacher effectiveness.

Rationale

The usefulness and effectiveness of the education system largely depends upon the active, resourceful and competent teachers. Teacher's competence, capability and effectiveness make schools good or bad, flourishing or deteriorating. Hence quality of teaching depends upon the efficiency of the teachers. Beside other cognitive and non cognitive variables, job satisfaction influences teacher's performance, students' achievement, work motivation, organisational commitment and teacher's efficacy. Satisfaction provides happiness and contentment to the teacher, whereas dissatisfaction from the job indicates negative feelings

towards work. How satisfaction is related with the effectiveness of the teacher, is the question which this study is going to be answered.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To identify highly effective and less effective teachers of the secondary schools of Punjab
2. To study and compare job satisfaction of highly effective and less effective teachers.
3. To study job satisfaction as correlates of teacher effectiveness.
4. To make recommendations and suggestions on the basis of the findings of the study.

Hypotheses

1. There is significant difference in job satisfaction of highly effective and less effective secondary school teachers.
2. Teacher effectiveness is positively correlated with job satisfaction.

Methodology and Procedure

Sample a representative sample of 1000 teachers was selected from the government secondary schools of four districts of Punjab. As per Census of India, two districts Ludhiana and Patiala were selected from the category of educationally advanced districts and other two Muktsar and Mansa from educationally backward districts. Teacher effectiveness of the teachers was studied by using Teacher Effectiveness scale by Kumar and Mutha. Fulfilling the first objective of the study, the identification of highly effective and less effective group of teachers was done by two ways (a) the manual of the teacher effectiveness scale shows that teachers having score between 307-329 are highly effective and teachers having the score between 250-285 are less effective. According to this norm, 213 teachers were identified as highly effective and 203 came out to be less effective teachers. Job satisfaction of teachers was studied by Sharma and Singh Job Satisfaction scale.

TABLE – 1
JOB SATISFACTION SCORES OF TEACHERS

Effectiveness	N	Mean	Md.	Mode	S.D.	t	Significance
Highly Effective	200	74.35	74.12	74.66	9.03	5.61	P<0.01
Less Effective	200	69.14	69.04	68.84	6.51		
Total	1000	71.75	71.15	70.95	9.63		

Fig showing job satisfaction of highly effective, less effective and total group of teachers

Table 1 shows that mean score in job satisfaction for highly effective teachers is 74.35 with S.D. 9.03 and for less effective teachers mean score is 69.14 with S.D. 6.51. According to the norms of the scale, subjects with score of 74 or above are extremely satisfied with their jobs and teachers with score between 63 and 73 are satisfied, 56-62 are moderately satisfied and 48-55 are not satisfied. In the present study for highly effective teachers mean job satisfaction score is 74.35, thus they fall in the extremely satisfied category. The score for less effective teachers is 69.14 which fall in the category of just satisfied group.

The t-value standing at 5.61, is significant at 0.01 level of confidence. This indicates that although, both the groups are satisfied with their jobs but the less effective group significantly differs from the highly effective group and the difference is in favour of highly effective group. The interpretation is not difficult to make that highly effective teacher is more satisfied and the teacher who is less effective draws lesser satisfaction from his work. His psyche contains an element of guilt, which results in dissatisfaction. This happens despite the fact that both the categories of teachers are equally placed in terms of salary, placement, environmental conditions, job security etc. The satisfied teacher certainly makes full efforts to do the job effectively. Further, his effective performance in and outside the classroom situations provides him more satisfaction, which again accelerates his effectiveness. On the other hand, a dissatisfied or less satisfied teacher views his job as a burden and this dissatisfaction ultimately impairs his effectiveness.

Table 2
Correlation Coefficients between Teacher effectiveness and Job Satisfaction

Effectiveness	Job satisfaction
Highly Effective	.779** (10.510)
Less Effective	.461**

	(5.381)
Total	.601** (9.912)

Table 2 indicates that the coefficient of correlation between teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction of the highly effective group is .779 and of less effective group is .461. In case of highly effective group, the value of correlation coefficient is high and positive, whereas in case of less effective group it is only moderate but positive. The difference between the coefficients of highly effective and less effective group is significant at .01 level of confidence. Two conclusions emerge, firstly, teacher effectiveness has job satisfaction as its correlate secondly, as effectiveness lowers job satisfaction also lowers and the two groups i.e. the highly effective and less effective group are statistically differ on the variable of job satisfaction.

Table 2 also reveals that the correlation coefficient of teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction for the total group is .601. This value is very high and positive. It gives a conclusion that job satisfaction is definitely a positive correlate of teacher effectiveness. The findings of the present study correspond to the findings of the studies done by Lavingia (1974), Singh (1985) and Noll (2004), who found in their respective studies that job satisfaction correlates positively with the teacher effectiveness.

Conclusion

The present study points out in unequivocal terms that highly effective teachers are more satisfied with their jobs than less effective teachers. Further, the study has shown that job satisfaction is a positive correlate of teacher effectiveness. It is thus recommended that steps should be taken to ensure maximum job satisfaction among teachers in order to accelerate their effectiveness. It has been seriously observed that most of the Govt. schools lack basic facilities and infrastructure, which may be the cause of dissatisfaction among school teachers. So, it is

suggested that the facilities and working conditions of the Govt schools should be augmented liberally. Highly qualified teachers at low grade posts feel job dissatisfaction, so promotion avenues should be opened for the teachers. There should be a regular exchange of teachers working in rural and urban schools. It will reduce boredom and ensure uniform standards of teaching. Time to time, guidance and counselling programmes, refresher courses, should be organised for teachers so that teachers may discuss their problems and causes of dissatisfaction.

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